

The power of standardisation: Adopting the OMOP CDM to enable insights from cardiac benchmarking across multiple European paediatric centres

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ABSTRACT

Electronic patient record (EPR) data is a rich source of information which has revolutionised patient care and the ability to conduct research. However, hospitals may use different coding standards and vocabularies to capture similar medical information which can make it difficult to conduct collaborative research. Through the standardisation of medical data by utilising, for example, the **Observations Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model (OMOP CDM)** and the use of a **federated data network**, it becomes possible for multiple sites to work together for the benefit of patient health and operational management. The PHEMS project includes 4 European paediatric hospitals (HUS - Helsinki, GOSH - London, SJD - Barcelona, Erasmus - Rotterdam).

PHEMS NETWORK The Paediatric Hospitals as European drivers for Multi-party computation and Synthetic data generation capabilities across clinical specialities and data types

4 hospitals have standardised their data to the **OMOP CDM** – an open community data standard designed to standardise the structure and content of observational data.

The study period spans from May 2019 to February 2025 and includes patients who have records pertaining to a selection of defined **cardiac operations**. GOSH's base cohort contains 2,605 patients (55.3 % male, 44.7 % female, median age 0 years).

The cardiac use-case is developed to **benchmark** patient pathways across hospitals. Including investigating differences in; post surgery complications, hospital length of stay, and survival analyses.

Characterisation of the data highlights key findings relating to **30-day complication rate** post cardiac operation, which can be tracked over time, and **includes time-to-event information** to investigate onset of such complications.

Figure 2:

GOSH's OMOP database is being continuously developed, containing more and more data since 2019 (Figure 1). Through open-source packages which work with a sites' OMOP database, analyses on cohorts can be conducted.

Figure 2: The median length of stay for patients undergoing a VSD repair is less than a patient receiving a cardiac pacemaker (8 vs 11 days), Figure 3: The 10 most common diagnoses for patients 90 days post heart transplant.

Figure 3:

